

THIOCYANAMIDES AND SULPHONITRILES : THEIR CONSTITUTION AND IDENTITY

BY R. H. SAHASRABUDHEY

It has been shown that the thiocyanamide of Freund and Schander and aromatic sulphonitriles of Oliveri-Mandala are identical with formamidine disulphide and the corresponding aminoarylthiazoles respectively.

Freund and Schander (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2500) by the action of concentrated hydrochloric acid on 'amidothiotriazole' obtained the hydrochloride, $\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_2\text{,HCl}$ of a base which they called thiocyanamide. Later, Oliveri-Mandala (*Gazzetta*, 1914, 44, 670) showed that the 'amidothiotriazoles' were really thiocarbamic acid azides, and by the action of hydrochloric acid on phenyl-, tolyl- and ethyl-thiocarbamic acid azides prepared the salts of the corresponding thiocyanamides which he called sulphonitriles :

No attempt seems to have been made by him or by any other worker to prepare the parent thiocyanamide, viz. $\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_2\text{,Cl}$ of Freund and Schander, or to examine its constitution. The generic relationship obtaining between the thiocyanamides and the sulphonitriles *i.e.*, the proved identity (i) of Freund's triazoles and tetrazoles (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 74 ; 1896, 29, 2491) with the azides obtained by Oliveri-Mandala (*loc. cit.*) and (ii) of ethylthiocyanamide (*Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, 98) obtained by both the workers, rendered such an enquiry apparently unnecessary.

Freund and Schander have discussed the constitution of thiocyanamide for which they favoured a three membered ring structure (*loc. cit.*). Oliveri-Mandala represented it as a sulphonitrile, while more recently (Adams, "Organic Reactions," Vol. III, 1946, p. 362) it has been given the constitution of an *isothiocyanamine* : Thus

These constitutions have been built up from an erroneous composition assumed for the compound to suit the mechanism of its formation as laid down by Freund and Schander, and by Oliveri-Mandala. Analytically determined, the hydrochlorides of thiocyanamide and its methyl homologue have the composition $\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4\text{,Cl}$ and $\text{C}_2\text{SN}_2\text{H}_6\text{,Cl}$ respectively and not $\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_3\text{,Cl}$ or $\text{C}_2\text{SN}_2\text{H}_5\text{,Cl}$ as hitherto assumed (Freund and Schander, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 2504, 2499). Further, these formulatious do not take into account the fact that free bases of these salts, excepting those from aromatic thiocyanamides, have been shown incapable of free existence.

Formation of thiocyanamide from thiocarbamic acid azide and the identity of its composition with the empirical composition of formamidine disulphide (hydrochloride, $\text{CSN}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$), the oxidation product of thiocarbamide, suggested to the author that they might be identical.

The expectation has been fully realised. This, however, in the opinion of the author, does not settle the question of its constitution which is being examined separately.

The constitution of the aromatic thiocyanamides or sulphonitriles cannot be identical with the corresponding formamidine disulphides, because aryl derivatives of the latter are known not to exist, whilst free bases from the salts of the former have been prepared and even their molecular weights determined. The structure assigned to them by Oliveri-Mandala (*loc. cit.*, 1922), since it assumes a penta-covalent nitrogen, is clearly untenable. In the light of the work of Fischer and Besthorn (*Annalen*, 1882, 212, 316) and Hegershoff (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3134), it appears more than probable that they are identical with the corresponding aminoarylthiazoles :

where R is a hydrogen atom or an alkyl residue. A comparison of the melting points given by Oliveri-Mandala (*loc. cit.*) with those of the corresponding arylaminothiazoles almost proves their identity :

Aniline sulphonitrile ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{S}$), m.p. 122-123° ; aminobenzthiazole ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{S}$), m.p. 123° ; *o*-toluidine sulphonitrile ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}$), m.p. 138-40° ; amino-*o*-toluthiazole ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}$), m.p. 140°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and Properties of Thiocyanamide.—Thiocyanamide hydrochloride was prepared from 'amidothiotriazole' by Freund and Schander's procedure (*loc. cit.*).

Its saline character is evident from its easy solubility in water and alcohol and insolubility in ether, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and benzene. Its aqueous solutions are highly acid due to hydrolysis. Free base cannot be isolated from it, but on addition of alkali to its solutions sulphur is precipitated and thiocarbamide and cyanamide are formed in solution. The thiocyanamide salts liberate iodine from aqueous potassium iodide solutions.

Reduction of Thiocyanamide Hydrochloride.—On reduction of an aqueous solution of thiocyanamide hydrochloride with zinc and hydrochloric acid, large quantities of hydrogen sulphide were evolved and some free sulphur deposited. The solution was filtered free from sulphur and a part of it treated with excess of NaOH solution when no precipitation of sulphur was observed, indicating the absence of unreduced thiocyanamide. The rest of the solution was then made ammoniacal and zinc precipitated as ZnS with hydrogen sulphide and filtered out. The filtrate thus freed from sulphur, zinc salts

and thiocyanamide on concentration deposited crystals of thiocarbamide in a syrupy residue which proved to be cyanamide.

Identity of Thiocyanamide Salts with Formamidine Disulphide Salts.—The nitrate, picrate and the hydrobromide of thiocyanamide were prepared by treating the aqueous solutions of its hydrochloride with the appropriate acids: Hydrochloride, m.p. 186° (d); hydrobromide, m.p. 185-190° (d); nitrate, m.p. 82° or 140° (d); picrate, m.p. 154° or 164° (d).

The melting points of the various salts, as will be evident, are identical with those of the corresponding salts of formamidine disulphide (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1948, Part III, p. 25). On determining the melting points of the mixtures of the respective salts from both the sources no depression was recorded, confirming their identity.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY.

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